

Mapping of existing E-PRTR and LCP datasets into the EU Registry and E-PRTR/LCP databases

Draft methodology for consultation

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Executive summary

This document provides an overview of a process by which historical E-PRTR and LCP data can be imported into the new data structures for the EU Registry and the E-PRTR and LCP integrated reporting (Thematic) dataflows, while ensuring the data remains Inspire compliant. The aim is to support the implementation and testing of the mapping process.

A review of the E-PRTR and LCP databases provided an overview of how the data can be mapped into the new databases. The individual reporting country has a major role in the process of mapping.

The databases consist of records of different types of pollutant releases and transfers. These thematic data sets are different for each database. This document maps the structure of thematic data from LCP and E-PRTR datasets into new EU Registry and E-PRTR and LCP Integrated Reporting databases (see Figure ES.1), and gives the input that is needed from the individual reporting countries to support the mapping process, including the time frame. It also describes how new fields in the EU Registry and E-PRTR/LCP databases will be populated as part of the process, and gives the reporting countries relevant tables to provide Inspire identifiers for each facility.

Figure ES.1: Illustration of datatype and dataflow from E-PRTR and LCP into EU Registry

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This report was prepared for consultation with EEA member countries regarding new regime of reporting of industrial emissions, in ETC/ATNI task 1.2.5.2 for 2019. The EEA task manager was Ian Marnane. The ETC task manager was Eva Krtkova (CHMI). Laurence Opie (Aether) was reviewer of the report and provided invaluable advice. Mark Gibs (Aether) provided further support to the task.

1 Introduction

This document provides a draft mapping methodology, detailing the most efficient process by which historical E-PRTR and LCP data can be imported into the new data structures for the EU Registry and the E-PRTR and LCP integrated reporting (Thematic) dataflows, while ensuring the data remains Inspire compliant. In order to provide an integrated database of all historical E-PRTR and LCP thematic data it is necessary to import all previously reported E-PRTR and LCP annual datasets into the new database structures. This will require engagement with reporters in order to define the relationships between different datasets, such as between historical E-PRTR facilities and LCPs. This document is required to support the implementation and testing of the mapping process.

Firstly a review of the E-PRTR and LCP databases was carried out with the aim of finding out how the data can be mapped into the new databases. Importantly, this document identifies the role of the reporting country in the process of mapping the databases.

The main parts of the databases contain records of different type of pollutant releases and transfers. These thematic data sets are different for each database. This document maps the structure of thematic data from LCP and E-PRTR datasets into new EU Registry and E-PRTR and LCP Integrated Reporting databases (see Figure 1.1).

Finally this document indicates the information and input that is needed from reporting countries to support the mapping process, including the time frame, and identifies how new fields in the EU Registry and E-PRTR/LCP databases will be populated as part of the process.

This consultation document is based on firstly mapping the E-PRTR historical dataset and then, once this mapping has been validated, implementing the mapping of the LCP dataset into the new databases. This will simplify the process of validating the data mapping.

For comparison of databases the following sources for the structure of E-PRTR, LCP and EU Registry databases was used:

- for E-PRTR: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/member-states-reporting-art-7-under-the-european-pollutant-release-and-transfer-register-e-prtr-regulation-21>
- for LCP: the 2016 Czech Republic LCP database submission;
- for the EU Registry data model: **Data Modelling Report EU Registry on Industrial Sites**, Author: Stefania Morrone, 2018;
- for the E-PRTR and LCP integrated reporting data model: **E-PRTR and LCP integrated reporting - Data model documentation**, EEA 2018.

Figure 1.2: Illustration of datatype and dataflow from E-PRTR and LCP into EU Registry

2 Step 1: Mapping of E-PRTR into EU Registry

2.1 Identifiers in E-PRTR in relation to EU Registry

The Inspire identifier (InspireID) is the key identifier in the EU Registry, however currently it is not linked to the historical E-PRTR database structure. Within the historical E-PRTR dataset the key identifier for an E-PRTR facility is the NationalID. In order to import the historical E-PRTR data it will be necessary to assign an InspireID to all facilities in the current E-PRTR database. It is therefore necessary that reporters in each country assign InspireIDs to the NationalIDs in the E-PRTR database. The EEA/ETC propose to provide the reporting countries with relevant tables to provide Inspire identifiers for each facility (please see Annex 1). Furthermore, the reporters will also be requested to provide the InspireID for the associated site.

Reported years 2007 – 2017 under E-PRTR will be mapped into the EU Registry, with the exception of EU registry data for 2017, with 2017 data being reported to the EU Registry in June 2019.

In some cases the NationalID of a facility in the E-PRTR database has changed over the years. This is addressed in the E-PRTR database and an internal FacilityID is also assigned to each facility. In this case more than one NationalID may be associated with each FacilityID. It is crucial that reporters provide a single InspireID for each facility, irrespective of whether the facility has had multiple NationalIDs over different reporting years.

If the facility and site are reported in the first reporting round in June 2019 in the EU Registry submission, the data for the site (i.e. location, name) will be copied and used as the site information for the years prior to 2017. In cases where the facility and site are not reported in the first reporting round in June 2019 in the EU Registry submission, the EEA/ETC will generate the data for the site (i.e. location, name will be based on the facility name and location).

Once the relationships between facilities and sites are established, the relevant data fields will then be mapped from the existing E-PRTR database into the new EU Registry and Thematic database structures.

In cases where a facility is reported only for some years, the administrative data (i.e. the EU Registry information) can be gap-filled for the missing years. No thematic data will be created for these gap-filled years. Using the Inspire ID the data will be added into the time-series.

Key input required from reporters

The ETC/EEA will generate a list of all NationalIDs in the historical E-PRTR database, which will be sent to the reporters. Reporters will be required to provide the necessary data on the Inspire IDs. The provided tables will also include the facility name, location and years for which facility was reported to E-PRTR. This provides additional contextual data for reporters to assist in the data and site review.

Table 2.1 provides an example of completed data from the E-PRTR datasets and highlights the data which will be required from reporters, a blank table is provided in Annex 1.

Table 2.3: Required fields to report by reporters – example of provided data from E-PRTR datasets

Identifier E-PRTR of Facility	Identifier Inspire	Name of Facility	Identifier Inspire of site	Location of facility		Years of reporting to E-PRTR	Annex I Activity Code E-PRTR EU Reg. 166/2006
			Inspire ID of site	Longitude	Latitude		
NationalID	Inspire ID						
CZ44746297		Elektrárna Počeradý		13,67737	50,42667	2007 - 2017	1.(c)

2.2 Details of data fields

NationalID is a unique number allocated within reporting countries and is mostly an alphanumeric string (a combination of letters and numbers), this number is unique throughout the EU. For reporting to the EU Registry it is necessary to allocate a unique ID, compliant with the requirements of the Inspire Directive, to each E-PRTR facility. This ID is the **Inspire ID**.

The **Inspire ID** is the key identifier which needs to be provided for all levels in the EU Registry data model. This attribute is the fundamental building block that enables the effective sharing of geospatial environmental information. The EU provides guidance on how Inspire IDs unique to each country can be defined. Reporting country will have the flexibility to use their national identifiers provided they comply with the Inspire requirements for such IDs . The identifier value must be unique at each data model level throughout the reporting country.

Years of reporting in E-PRTR

This field provides details of all years for which data is available in the E-PRTR database for that facility. Years of reporting to E-PRTR need to be known because of a possible change in National ID in a time series. If the National ID has changed during the reporting years, it will be necessary to fill a multiple NationalIDs in the NationalID column while keeping single row for each facility.

Name of Facility is included in the table mainly for information and control reasons. The name of Facility will allow relatively easy checking that the assigned Inspire ID matches a given NationalID (when comparing two databases).

Location is also an important control element in ensuring that the facility has been correctly identified.

Annex I activity Code E-PRTR is included to provide further contextual data for reporters to ensure that facilities are correctly identified.

3 Mapping of LCP dataset into EU Registry

3.1 Identifiers in LCP in relation to EU Registry

The Inspire identifier (Inspire ID) is key identifier in the EU Registry, however for now it is not linked to the historical LCP dataset. It is therefore necessary that reporters in each country assign Inspire ID to the PlantID in the LCP. The EEA/ETC will provide the countries with relevant tables to provide Inspire identifiers for each plant (please see Annex 1). Further the reporters may also have to provide Inspire IDs for the parent installation, facility and site (but only in cases where the plant is not included in the June 2019 EU Registry submission).

Initially only data for the reported years 2016 and 2017 under LCP will be mapped into the EU Registry due to inconsistencies in the data format in previously reported LCP datasets. The mapping methodology will therefore be relatively simple for those LCPs which are reported to the EU Registry in the first round of reporting in June 2019, as this will already provide information on the parent installation, facility and site.

If the LCP is reported in the first reporting round in June 2019 (2017 reporting year data) in the EU Registry submission, then the parent installation, facility and site details will be used also for year 2016.

In case when the LCP is not reported in the first reporting round in June 2019 in the EU Registry submission, it will be necessary to generate installation, facility and site level data for 2016, and this will require reporters to provide the Inspire ID for the installation, facility and site. If data needs to be generated for mandatory fields (e.g. installationName, FacilityName, locations) the data from the LCP database will be used (e.g. using the LCP Plant Name for the facility name but adding (facility) at the end, also using the LCP location for installation, facility and site level). It is expected that the majority of LCPs reported in 2016 will also be reported in 2017 and hence the need to generate data for installation, facility and site level is expected to be minimal.

Key input required from reporters

The ETC/EEA will generate list of the PlantIDs, which will be sent to the reporters with required fields to be filled in. The reporters, will have to provide Inspire IDs:

- If the LCP plant is reported in the June 2019 EU Registry submission then only the InspireID for the LCP plant is required;
- If the LCP plant is not reported in the June 2019 EU Registry submission then the Inspire IDs for the associated installation, facility and site will be required;

Table 3.1 provides an example of completed data from the LCP datasets and highlights the data which will be required from reporters, a blank table is provided in Annex 1.

Table 3.1: Required Inspire IDs from reporters – example of provided data from LCP datasets

Identifier of Plant	Reported only in 2016	Identifier Inspire	Name of Plant	Identifier Inspire of site	Inspire ID of facility*	Inspire ID of Installation *	Plant Location	
Plant ID	Yes/No	Inspire ID		Inspire ID of site			Longitude	Latitude
CZ0048			Elektrarna Pocerady, a.s.		Elektrárna Počerady, a.s.		13.67737	50.42667

* Facility Name and Installation will be completed in case the facility is decommissioned before 2017 and therefore is not reported in the June 2019 EU Registry submission

3.2 Details of data fields

PlantID is a unique number allocated within each EU member states and is mostly an alphanumeric string (a combination of letters and numbers), this number should be unique throughout the EU. The EU Registry requires a unique identifier for each Plant. This ID is the **Inspire ID**.

The Inspire ID needs to be provided for all levels in the data model. This attribute is the fundamental building block that enables the effective sharing of geospatial environmental information. The EU provides guidance on how Inspire IDs unique to each country can be defined. Reporting country will have the flexibility to use their national identifiers provided they comply with the Inspire requirements for such IDs . The identifier value must be unique at each data model level throughout the reporting country.

Name of Plant will be included in the data table (see Table 3.1) mainly for control reasons. The Name of Plant will allow relatively easy checking that the assigned Inspire ID matches a given PlantID (when comparing two databases).

Location is also an important control element. When using map backgrounds, it is useful to be able to check the correct identification of the plant.

The data table will also indicate if the PlantID was only reported in 2016 (and not in 2017). For these site that were only reported in 2016, reporters will need to provide the Inspire ID for the associated installation, facility and site.

4 QA/QC checks on the mapped data

The EEA/ETC will run QA/QC checks on the data imported into the EU Registry and Thematic databases. The check will focus on the data reported under the E-PRTR, LCP and their relevant fields in the EU Registry. These checks will help to ensure that the data has been accurately mapped into the new database structure.

It is possible, that during these checks the EEA/ETC will evaluate, that more information from the countries will be needed in order to map the data reported under the E-PRTR and LCP into the EU Registry. In that case the countries and relevant authorities will be contacted later in 2019 to provide relevant data.

5 Data collection and mapping time-frame

5.1 Time frame

April 2019: Circulation of this consultation document. Reporters will have 4 weeks to provide comments and feedback.

May 2019: Finalisation of the mapping methodology based on feedback from reporters.

June 30 2019: deadline for reporting to EU Registry.

July 2019: Issue data tables to reporters to complete necessary information.

October: Complete mapping exercise and carry out QA checks on imported data. Request additional information from reporting countries as needed.

The EEA/ETC will provide reporters with the tables in Annex 1 during July 2019. The reporters will be asked to fill Inspire IDs to the NationalID under the E-PRTR, and further Inspire IDs to the PlantID under the LCP and further details were required (such as associated Inspire IDs for the installation, facility and site level).

5.2 Key Questions for Reporters

Reporters are invited to provide their general feedback on the proposed mapping methodology and any difficulties or barriers which they see in relation to this process. However, the EEA/ETC would also encourage reporters to respond to these specific questions below.

1. Are there any barriers to providing the necessary data as identified in the methodology, i.e. can you provide Inspire identifiers for all historical NationalIDs (for E-PRTR) and PlantIDs (for LCP data)?
2. Do you have any concerns in relation to the proposal for gap-filling of years in the EU Registry?
3. Do you have any concerns in relation to the timeframes outlined in Section 6 of this document?
4. Do you have any other comments or concern in relation to the proposed mapping process?

Annex 1 – Required data from reporters

These tables will be provided to reporters in xls format.

Table A1.1: Required data from reporters – E-PRTR datasets

Identifier E-PRTR of Facility	Identifier Inspire	Name of Facility	Identifier Inspire of site	Location of facility		Years of reporting to E-PRTR	Annex I Activity Code E-PRTR EU Reg. 166/2006
NationalID	Inspire ID		Inspire ID of site	Longitude	Latitude		

Table A1.2: Required data from reporters – LCP datasets

Identifier of Plant	Reported only in 2016	Identifier Inspire	Name of Plant	Identifier Inspire of site	Inspire ID of facility*	Inspire ID of Installation*	Plant Location	
Plant ID	Yes/No	Inspire ID		Inspire ID of site			Longitude	Latitude

*) Facility Name and Installation will be completed in case the facility is decommissioned before 2017 and therefore is not reported in the June 2019 EU Registry submission

Annex 2 – Dataflow from E-PRTR into EU Registry

Table A2.1: Pattern of interconnection E-PRTR datasets and new EU Registry

E-PRTR feature type	E-PRTR data type	EU Registry feature type	EU Register data type	EU Registry field	Format
FACILITY REPORT		ProductionFacility	EU Registry number	identifier	Code
	FacilityID	ProductionFacility	E-PRTR number	facilityId	Code
	NationalID		Inspire number	Inspire ID	Code
	ParentCompanyName	ProductionFacility	Parent Company Details	parentCompanyName	Character String
		ProductionFacility	Parent Company Details	parentCompanyURL	Character String
	FacilityName	ProductionFacility	Facility Details	facilityName	Character String
	StreetName	ProductionFacility	Facility Details	streetName	Character String
	BuildingNumber	ProductionFacility	Facility Details	buildingNumber	number
	City	ProductionFacility	Facility Details	city	Character String
	PostalCode	ProductionFacility	Facility Details	postalCode	Character String
	CountryCode	ProductionFacility	Country Code	countryCode	Code
	CountryName				
	Lat	ProductionFacility	Lokality details	localId	number
	Long	ProductionFacility	Lokality details	localId	number
	NUTSRegionSourceCode	ProductionFacility	NUTS Code	NUTS_1	Code
	NACEMainEconomicActivityCode	ProductionFacility	NACE Code	NACE	Code
		ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority ID	Id	number
	CompetentAuthorityName	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	competentAuthorityEPRT	Character String
		ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	organisationName	Character String
	CompetentAuthorityAddressStreetName	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	streetName	Character String

E-PRTR feature type	E-PRTR data type	EU Registry feature type	EU Register data type	EU Registry field	Format
	CompetentAuthorityAddressBuildingNumber	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	buildingNumber	number
	CompetentAuthorityAddressCity	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	city	Character String
	CompetentAuthorityAddressPostalCode	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	postalCode	number
	CompetentAuthorityTelephoneCommunication	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	contact details	telephoneNo	number
	CompetentAuthorityFaxCommunication	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	contact details	faxNo	number
	CompetentAuthorityEmailCommunication	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	electronicMailAddress	Character String
	CompetentAuthorityContactPersonName	ProductionFacilityAuthorityEPRT	Authority details	individualName	Character String
		ProductionSite	Production details	ID	Code
	ProductionVolumeProductName	ProductionSite	Production details	Name	Character String
	ProductionVolumeQuantity	ProductionVolumeType	Production details	productionVolume	Number
	ProductionVolumeUnitCode	ProductionVolumeType	Production details	productionVolumeUnits	Code
	OperatingHours	ProductionFacilityReport	Production details	numberOfOperatingHours	Number
	RemarkText	ProductionFacility		Remarks	Character String
ACTIVITY	AnnexIActivityCode	ProductionFacility		EPTRAnnexIMainActivity	Code
POLLUTANT RELEASE	ReleaseMediumCode	PollutantRelease	New in EU Registry	mediumCode	Code
	PollutantCode	PollutantRelease	Pollutant details	Pollutant	Code
	MethodBasisCode	PollutantRelease	Method details	method	Code
	TotalQuantity	PollutantRelease	Quantity of Pollutant	totalPollutantQuantityKg:	Number
	AccidentalQuantity	PollutantRelease	Acc. Quant. of Poll.	accidentalPollutantQuantityKg	Number
	ConfidentialIndicator	PollutantRelease			
	ConfidentialityReasonCode	PollutantRelease		confidentialityReason	Code
	ConfidentialityReasonName	PollutantRelease			
	RemarkText			Remarks	Character String
POLLUTANT RELEASE METHOD USED	MethodTypeCode	MethodType	MethodClassificationValue	methodCode	Code

E-PRTR feature type	E-PRTR data type	EU Registry feature type	EU Register data type	EU Registry field	Format	
	MethodDesignation		MethodType	furtherDetails	Character String	
POLLUTANT TRANSFER	PollutantCode		OffsitePollutantTransfer	pollutant		
	MethodBasisCode		OffsitePollutantTransfer	method	Code	
	Quantity		OffsitePollutantTransfer	totalPollutantQuantityKg	Character String	
WASTE TRANSFER	WasteTransferID		OffsiteWasteTransfer	Waste Classification	wasteClassification	Code
	WasteTreatmentCode		OffsiteWasteTransfer	Waste Treatment	wasteTreatment	Code
	MethodBasisCode		OffsiteWasteTransfer	Method of Waste Transfer	method	Code
	RemarkText			remarks		Character String

Annex 3 – Overview of new information in EU Registry and information about matching fields in E-PRTR and LCP

Some EU Registry fields do not have an equivalent field in the historical E-PRTR and LCP datasets and in some cases it may be necessary to generate entries for critical EU Registry fields.

Table A3.1: EU Registry newly required details

EU_reg - Grouping	FeatureType	dataType	codeList	Is there a matching field in E-PRTR or LCP databases	EU Registry new field that need to be populated	Comments on new EU Registry fields that need to be populated
ReportData	countryId		CountryCodeValue	Yes	No	
	reportingYear			Yes	No	
ProductionSite	location			No	Yes	If site is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there, otherwise use facility data.
	inspireId	localID		No	Yes	Provided by reporters.
		namespace		No	Yes	Provided by reporters.
	thematicID	identifier		No	No	
		identifierScheme		No	No	
	siteName	nemeOfFeature		No	Yes	If site is in EU Registry June 2017 dataset then take data from there, otherwise use facility data.
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	Yes	If confidentiality reason provided in June 2017 EU Registry data then copy for other years, otherwise leave blank.
ProductionFacility	facilityName	nameOfFeature		Yes	No	
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	No	
	competentAuthorityEPTR	organizationName		Yes	No	
		individualName		Yes	No	
		electronicMailAddress		Yes	No	
		address		Yes	No	
	telephoneNo			Yes	No	

EU_reg - Grouping	FeatureType	dataType	codeList	Is there a matching field in E-PRTR or LCP databases	EU Registry new field that need to be populated	Comments on new EU Registry fields that need to be populated
		faxNo		Yes	No	
	parentCompany	parentCompanyName		Yes	No	
		parent CompanyURL		Yes	No	
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	No	
	inspireId	localID		No	Yes	Provided by reporters.
		nameSpace		No	Yes	Provided by reporters.
	thematicID	identifier		No	No	
		identifierScheme		No	No	
	function	activity	EconomicActivityValue	Yes	No	
	EPRTAnnexActivity	mainActivity	EPRTAnnexIActivityValue	Yes	No	
		otherActivity	EPRTAnnexIActivityValue	Yes	No	
	remarks			Yes	No	
	geometry			Yes	No	
	address	streetName		Yes	No	
		buildingNumber		Yes	No	
		city		Yes	No	
		postalCode		Yes	No	
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	No	
	dateOfStartOfOperation			No	Yes	If facility is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there, otherwise leave blank.

EU_reg - Grouping	FeatureType	dataType	codeList	Is there a matching field in E-PRTR or LCP databases	EU Registry new field that need to be populated	Comments on new EU Registry fields that need to be populated
	status	statusType	conditionOfFacilityValue	No	Yes	Set all previous reported years to status 'functional' except where not reported in June 2019, then set most recent year of reporting to decommissioned and all years before that to 'functional'.
ProductionInstallation	instalationName	nameOfFeature		No	Yes	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there, otherwise use facility name.
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	No	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there, otherwise leave blank.
	baselineReportPreparedIndicator		BaselineReportValue	No	No	
	BAT Derogation	BAT DerogationIndicator		No	No	
		publicReasonURL		No	No	
		BATAEL	BATAELValue	No	No	
		derogationDurateStartDate		No	No	
		derogationDurateEndDate		No	No	
	competentAuthorityPermits			No	No	
	competentAuthorityInspection			No	No	
	siteVisit	sitevisitNumber		No	No	
		siteVisitURL		No	No	
	otherRelevantChapters		otherRelevantChaptersValue	No	No	
	permit	permitGranted		No	No	
		permitReconsidered		No	No	
		permitUpdated		No	No	
		dataOfGranting		No	No	

EU_reg - Grouping	FeatureType	dataType	codeList	Is there a matching field in E-PRTR or LCP databases	EU Registry new field that need to be populated	Comments on new EU Registry fields that need to be populated
		dateOfLastUpdate		No	No	
		permitURL		No	No	
		enforcementAction		No	No	
	IEDAnnexIActivity	mainActivity	IEDAnnexIActivityValue	No	No	
	eSPIRSid			No	No	
	ETSID			No	No	
	inspireId			No	Yes	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there based on inspireID of LCP plant, otherwise reporter has to provide installation inspireID.
	thematicID	identifier		No	No	
		identifierScheme		No	No	
	pointGeometry			No	Yes	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there based on inspireID of LCP plant, otherwise use reported LCP geometry as installation geometry.
	remarks			No	No	
	status	statusType	conditionOfFacilityValue	No	Yes	Status =functional
	stricterPermitConditions	stricterPermitConditionsIndicator		No	No	
		BATAEL	BATAELValue	No	No	
		article14.4		No	No	
		article18		No	No	
	publicEmissionMonitoring			No	No	
	publicEmissionMonitoringURL			No	No	
	BAT Conclusion		BAT ConclusionValue	No	No	
	InstalationType		InstalationTypeValue	No	Yes	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there based on inspireID of LCP plant, otherwise leave blank.

EU_reg - Grouping	FeatureType	dataType	codeList	Is there a matching field in E-PRTR or LCP databases	EU Registry new field that need to be populated	Comments on new EU Registry fields that need to be populated
	dateOfStartOfOperation			No	Yes	If installation is in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there based on inspireID of LCP plant, otherwise leave blank.
ProductionInstallationPart	instalationPartName	nameOfFeature		Yes	No	
		confidentialityReason	ReasonValue	No	No	
	plantType		PlantTypeValue	No	Yes	all LCPs should have plantType set to LCP - http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/euregistryonindustrialsites/PlantTypeValue/LCP
	derogation		DerogationValue	Yes		
	nominalCapacity	totalNominalWasteCapacityAnyWasteType		No	No	
		permittedCapacityHazardeous		No	No	
		permittedCapacityNonHazardeous		No	No	
	specificCondition	specificCondition	Article51Value	No	No	
	totalRatedThermalInput			Yes	No	
	inspireId			No	Yes	provided by reporters
	thematicID	identifier		No	No	
		identifierScheme		No	No	
	pointGeometry			Yes	No	
	status	statusType	conditionOfFacilityValue	No	Yes	Only need to set this for 2016 data as this is the only year of import. Set to functional.
	remarks			Yes	No	
	heatReleaseHazardeousWaste			No	No	
	untreatedMunicipalWaste			No	No	
	publicDiclosure			No	No	
	publicDiclosureURL			No	No	
	dateOfStartOfOperation			Yes	Yes	If in EU Registry June 2019 dataset then take data from there , otherwise leave blank.

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